

The Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility Characteristics on Organizational Commitment -- A Case Study of Guangdong Construction Enterprises

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Abstract

The corporate social responsibility movement originated in western developed countries. They also have an essential role that can directly contribute to or destroy their environmental and social ecology. This study analyzes the impact of corporate social responsibility features of construction enterprises in Guangdong Province on employees' organizational commitment along the two aspects of employees' psychological perception (organizational identification and organization-based self-esteem), and then from the logical thinking of employees' psychological perception to employees' organizational commitment. This study divides corporate social responsibility features into three dimensions: corporate social responsibility culture, corporate social responsibility atmosphere and corporate social responsibility performance. The empirical results of this study show that the three dimensions of corporate social responsibility features have a significant impact on organizational identification, corporate social responsibility performance has a significant impact on organization based self-esteem, while corporate social responsibility culture and corporate social responsibility atmosphere have no significant impact on organization based self-esteem; Organizational identification and organization based self-esteem have a significant impact on organizational commitment; Corporate social responsibility performance has a direct impact on organizational commitment, while corporate social responsibility atmosphere has no direct impact on organizational commitment; Organizational identification has a completely mediating role between corporate social responsibility culture and organizational commitment; Organizational identification has a completely mediating role between the corporate social responsibility atmosphere and the organizational commitment; The relationship between organizational identification and organization based self-esteem in corporate social responsibility and organizational commitment has some mediating roles.

Keywords: *Corporate social responsibility features, organization-based self-esteem, organizational identification, organizational commitment.*

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Introduction

The construction industry is a labor-intensive industry. In recent years, the front-line workers of construction enterprises have moved frequently, and the turnover rate of employees has continued to increase. The employment situation of enterprises is not optimistic. In today's increasingly prominent malpractice of simply pursuing economic development, corporate social responsibility has become an international hot topic. As a pillar industry of the national economy, the construction industry plays an increasingly important role in social production and life, and its influence is also growing. It has become a common expectation and requirement of modern society for construction enterprises to shoulder more responsibilities (Shi, 2020; Wang 2020; Su & Zang 2021). While seeing the continuous improvement of the practice level of corporate social responsibility in China, we should also recognize that many enterprises still have serious product quality problems, environmental pollution problems, consumer fraud, labor squeeze, safety production accidents and other problems. The Sanlu milk powder melamine incident, the Shanxi black brick kiln incident, and the repeated catastrophic mining accidents that once shocked the Chinese people all remind people that it is urgent to popularize the corporate social responsibility concept, improve the corporate social responsibility awareness, and change the social attitude of enterprises (Chi, 2021; Wen 2020; Zhang 2019).

Problem Statement

Corporate social responsibility features are the intrinsic essence of corporate social responsibility, which goes beyond the focus on the content of corporate social responsibility. They are a scarce and heterogeneous moral resource and one of the potential elements of enterprise soft power. Analyzing their impact on enterprise soft power and long-term competitive advantage is a detailed study and preliminary exploration of enterprise soft power theory (Chi, 2021; Zhang 2019; Su & Zang 2021). However, is corporate social responsibility a cost, burden or a cost-effective investment? This problem still puzzles many scholars. Most of the empirical studies on corporate social responsibility are also conducted from the perspective of corporate financial performance (Wang 2020; Wen 2020). Based on this, this paper takes construction enterprises in Guangdong Province as a sample to explore the relationship between corporate social responsibility features and employee organizational commitment through empirical research. Based on the above issues, this study focuses on the following questions:

- R. Q. 1: Does the corporate social responsibility feature affect the organizational identification and organization based self-esteem?
- R. Q. 2: Is there any influence among organizational identification, organization based self esteem and organizational commitment?
- R. Q. 3: Does the corporate social responsibility feature indirectly affect the organizational commitment through the organization based self-esteem and organizational identification?
- R. Q. 4: Is there a relationship between the corporate social responsibility feature and the organizational commitment?

Literature review

Corporate Social Responsibility Features

This study describes corporate social responsibility features from three dimensions: corporate social responsibility culture, social responsibility atmosphere and social responsibility performance (Lei, 2003). So far, there is no mature scale of corporate social responsibility culture. Therefore, it is advisable to draw lessons from the mature scale on corporate culture,

extract measurement clauses related to social responsibility from it, and develop a new scale in combination with enterprise interviews and expert opinions (Zhang & Dai, 2017).

The relatively mature measurement scales for corporate culture measurement include Cameron and Quinn (1999) organizational culture evaluation scale, Hofstede (1990) multi-dimensional organizational culture model measurement scale and Denison (1995) organizational culture model measurement scale. Cameron and Quinn's (1999) organizational culture evaluation scale is divided into six dimensions to measure: main features, leadership, employee management, organizational cohesion, strategic focus and success criteria. Cameron and Quinn's research mainly evaluates enterprise culture from the perspective of competitive value, but there is little analysis on the core part of enterprise culture: values. Therefore, this study only draws on its leadership dimension and revises and Supplements Articles 1-4 and 1-5 based on interviews with enterprise management. Hofstede (1990) extended the multi-dimensional organizational culture model measurement scale from the national cross-cultural research to the field of enterprise culture. From the perspective of values and practices, it divided enterprise culture into five dimensions: power distance, uncertainty avoidance, individual / collectivist tendency, positive / negative culture, and long / short-term orientation. This has much inspiration for this study. However, because its dimension setting is relatively abstract, this study draws more on Denison's (1995) organizational culture model measurement scale. This measurement scale measures the characteristics of corporate culture from the four dimensions of mission, consistency, input and adaptability from the perspective of corporate beliefs and assumptions, and divides the characteristics of corporate culture into four categories. The classification is relatively clear and reasonable, but there are as many as 60 measurement terms. According to Cho (2000), the differentiation validity of the four characteristics of culture has yet to be tested, and the load value of some measurement terms is not high (Fang, 2012). Therefore, according to research needs, specific measurement clauses about enterprise mission, vision, enterprise spirit, ethical standards, values, etc. are selected, and corresponding modifications are made according to enterprise interview results and expert opinions to form clauses 1-1, 1-2, 1-3, 1-7, 1-8, 1-9, etc. (Song et al., 2017). Clauses 1-6 are added based on enterprise interviews (Wang, 1994). Finally, the initial scale of corporate social responsibility culture is formed, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Initial measurement scale of corporate social responsibility culture

No.	Measurement clause
1-1	The mission of the enterprise includes the content of common development and return to the society.
1-2	The long-term goal of the enterprise is worth fighting for.
1-3	The enterprise has the spirit of self-improvement and pursuing harmony.
1-4	Senior leaders of enterprises actively advocate the concept of social responsibility.
1-5	Senior leaders of enterprises set an example to promote the construction of social responsibility.
1-6	Enterprises have the practice of social responsibility.
1-7	Enterprises abide by laws and regulations and require employees to do so.
1-8	Enterprises require employees to be honest and trustworthy and abide by professional ethics.
1-9	Enterprises hope that employees can live in harmony and help each other.

(Source: Elnagar et al., 2022; DyeR&Denison, 2004)

So far, there is no mature scale of corporate social responsibility atmosphere. Therefore, we draw lessons from the maturity scale of similar ethical atmosphere, extract the measurement clauses related to social responsibility, and other special atmospheres, such as the maturity scale of innovation atmosphere, and develop a new scale in combination with enterprise interviews. Victor and Cullen (1987) took the lead in the study of organizational ethical climate, and then developed a measurement questionnaire to measure ethical climate. The questionnaire divided ethical climate into nine categories and five orientations, namely

instrumentalism orientation (self-interest orientation), care orientation, rule orientation, law and norm orientation, and independence orientation (Li & Wang, 2003). Victor and Cullen's questionnaires have been proved by many studies to have high reliability and validity, but some of them are not stable in different cultures and organizations. Moreover, the structure of this questionnaire is too complex to draw a clear framework, so only part of it is selected as one of the structures of the corporate social responsibility atmosphere (Zeng et al., 2017). Because the rule orientation is unstable, this study excludes it, while the independent orientation is in the relevant interviews of enterprises. Most enterprises, even those with better social responsibilities, do not agree that employees should act according to their own moral judgment and not be bound by the enterprise, so they have no choice. The legal and normative orientation has been reflected in the corporate social responsibility culture, and because the main development is the scale related to the social responsibility atmosphere, only the care orientation is selected and modified according to the interview results of enterprises, forming the measurement clauses of care orientation in the corporate social responsibility atmosphere: 1-10, 1-11, 1-12, 1-13 (Xiang & Wang, 2019). Referring to Stollberger et al. (2017) on the measurement of organizational innovation climate, it divides the innovation climate into four dimensions: vision, participation security, task orientation and innovation support. Its structure is reasonable, easy to measure in enterprises, and has good reliability and validity. Therefore, with reference to its structure, the support orientation is selected, and the corresponding social responsibility clauses are modified. In combination with enterprise interviews and expert interviews, the measurement clauses of social responsibility support orientation are determined as follows: 1-14, 1-15, 1-16 and 1-17. In data processing, Michael and West often separated some terms related to communication from participation safety, so they chose it as the communication orientation, modified the corresponding social responsibility terms, and determined the following social responsibility support orientation measurement terms in combination with enterprise interviews and expert interviews: 1-18, 1-19, 1-20, 1-21 (Zhu, 2020). Finally, the initial scale of corporate social responsibility atmosphere is formed, as shown in Table 2.

No.	Measurement clause
Care oriented	
1-10	Enterprises attach importance to the interests and development of employees.
1-11	Enterprises expect employees to do things that are beneficial to society.
1-12	Employees also care about the interests and development of their colleagues.
1-13	For the benefit of the enterprise, most employees do not hesitate to sacrifice their own interests.
Support oriented	
1-14	Enterprises carry out social responsibility education for employees.
1-15	Enterprises set up love funds to provide practical support for social responsibility.
1-16	Enterprises encourage employees to carry out social responsibility activities and use enterprise resources to support.
1-17	Enterprises will provide practical financial support when employees are in difficulties.
Communication oriented	
1-18	Enterprises encourage employees to keep informal organizational contact.
1-19	The communication channels between the senior management and the grass-roots are smooth.
1-20	Employees of the enterprise supervise and urge each other in social responsibility actions.
1-21	Enterprises often organize publicity activities to promote the exchange and understanding of social responsibility.

(Source: Victor & Cullen, 1987; Stollberger et al., 2017)

Corporate social responsibility performance (behavior) is measured by the corporate social responsibility orientation scale prepared by Aupperle, Carroll & Hatfield (1985). The scale is based on the four framework model of corporate social responsibility proposed by Carroll (1979), and is designed to measure the four dimensions of corporate social responsibility: economic responsibility, legal responsibility, ethical responsibility and charity responsibility (Ni, 2019). However, this scale only measures the attitude or view towards corporate social

responsibility, without the actual social responsibility behavior of the enterprise itself (Deng et al., 2017). Carroll's (1979) model has fuzzy responsibility boundaries. The limitation of overlapping responsibility standards and abstract responsibility attributes. Therefore, it is not used as a measurement tool in this study. The research of Zheng (2007), a domestic scholar, has been successful in the development of the corporate actual social responsibility behavior scale. With the help of the research results of the combination of stakeholder theory and corporate social responsibility, he divided corporate social responsibility behavior into three dimensions: responsibility for insiders (shareholders, employees, etc.), responsibility for external business partners (customers, suppliers, distributors, etc.), and responsibility for the public (environment, community, government, etc.) (Ge, 2020). Zheng established items by referring to relevant literature and enterprise interviews and conducted large sample surveys, which has high reliability and validity. Therefore, this study refers to its research results, and because of the limited capacity of the questionnaire, only the most representative stakeholders (employees, consumers, environment and community) in the three dimensions are selected to measure corporate social responsibility behavior, and at the same time, the terms are partially modified and supplemented according to the results of enterprise interviews and corporate donations after the 2008 Wenchuan earthquake (Li & Liu, 2017). The terms of social responsibility performance measurement are determined as follows: 1-22, 1-23, 1-24, 1-25, 1-26, etc. (Zhang, 2019). Finally, the initial scale of corporate social responsibility atmosphere is formed, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Initial measurement scale of corporate social responsibility performance

No.	Measurement clause
	Performance of corporate social responsibility to employees
1-22	The enterprise has signed labor contracts with all employees in accordance with the new labor law.
1-23	The average wage level of employees in the enterprise is competitive in the local area.
1-24	The enterprise has purchased social insurance such as pension and medical insurance for its employees.
1-25	The number of occupational diseases and industrial accidents of employees in enterprises is less than that of peers.
1-26	The enterprise's education and training of employees is better than that of its peers.
	Performance of corporate social responsibility to consumers
1-27	The quality management level of the enterprise has reached the level of ISO14000 series.
1-28	The information provided by enterprises to consumers is true and correct.
1-29	Enterprises handle consumer complaints quickly and timely.
1-30	There are few legal disputes between enterprises and consumers.
	Performance of corporate social responsibility to the public
1-31	Enterprises attach great importance to environmental protection.
1-32	Enterprises support local cultural, educational and sports undertakings.
1-33	The employment opportunities of enterprises give priority to local communities.
1-34	When a major disaster occurs in society, the amount of donations made by enterprises is higher than that of their peers.

(source: Zheng, 2007)

Organizational Identification

At present, the organizational identification measurement scale developed by Mael (1988, Mael and Ashforth, 1992) is more popular in the academic community. In addition, the organizational identification measurement scale of Cheney (1983) is also widely used. The organizational identification scale of Mael (1988) includes 6 items. The test shows that the internal consistency coefficient of the scale is 0.87, indicating that the scale has high internal consistency reliability (Mael and Ashforth, 1992). Cheney (1983)'s organizational identification measurement scale includes three dimensions and 25 terms. The internal consistency coefficient of the scale is 0.87, indicating that the scale has a high internal consistency reliability. However, according to the factor test results of barge and SCHLUETER (1998), the scale is one-dimensional (Zhang, 2019). After comparing the two, Riketta (2005) believes that the organizational identification scale of Mael (1988) is more concise and clear,

with better homogeneity among clauses and more effective construction validity. Therefore, this study mainly uses the organizational identification scale of Mael (1988) for reference to measure organizational identification, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Initial measurement scale of organizational identification

No.	Measurement clause
2-1	When someone criticizes my company, I feel ashamed.
2-2	I'm very interested in how other people view our company.
2-3	When talking about our company, I often use "we" instead of "they".
2-4	The success of this enterprise is my success.
2-5	When someone praises the company, it feels like praising myself.
2-6	When the media criticize our company on a certain subject, I feel uneasy.

(Source: Mael, 1988)

Organization Based Self-esteem

Currently, the organization-based self-esteem scale developed by Pierce, Gardner, Cummings et al. (1989) is recognized by the academic community. The scale includes 10 terms, and the internal consistency coefficient is 0.91, indicating that the scale has a high internal consistency reliability (Song, 2019). In addition, the scale has high aggregation validity, discrimination validity and prediction validity. Therefore, this study mainly uses this organization-based self-esteem measurement scale for reference to measure organization-based self-esteem, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5 Initial measurement scale of organization based self-esteem

No.	Measurement clause
2-7	I have a space for one person in my company.
2-8	I am a valued person in my company.
2-9	I am not important in my company.
2-10	My company trusts me.
2-11	I am an efficient person in my company.
2-12	I have influence over my company.
2-13	I am a valuable person in my company.
2-14	I am helpful to my company.
2-15	My company has confidence in me.
2-16	I am a cooperative person in my company.

(Source: Pierce et al, 1989)

Organizational Commitment

Mowday et al. (1979) developed the organizational commitment measurement scale, which includes 15 clauses. Allen and Meyer (1990) proposed the organizational commitment measurement scale, which includes three dimensions of emotional commitment, continuing commitment and normative commitment, and tested that the dimension of emotional commitment is significantly related to the organizational commitment measurement scale developed by Mowday, Steers and Porter (1979), with a correlation coefficient of 0.83. This shows that the original organizational commitment measurement scale mainly measures emotional commitment. In addition, emotional commitment and normative commitment also have a certain correlation, with a correlation coefficient of 0.51. Since then, they have partially simplified the measurement scale (Li & Zhang, 2017). Meyer, Stnaley, Herscovitch and Topolnytsky (2002) tested these scales respectively. The results show that the scale has reliable reliability and validity. Cheng and Stockgale (2003) examined Allen and Meyer's (1990) organizational commitment measurement scale in the context of Chinese culture, and found that Chinese employees' emotional commitment and normative commitment were higher than those of North American employees, while continuing commitment was the opposite (Liu, 2020). According to the research purpose of this study, organizational

commitment is measured by referring to the emotional commitment clause in Allen and Meyer's (1990) measurement scale, as shown in Table 6.

Table 6 Initial measurement scale of organizational commitment

No.	Measurement clause
3-1	I am happy to spend my future career in the current enterprise.
3-2	I feel that the problems of my company are my problems.
3-3	I don't feel that I belong to this enterprise emotionally.
3-4	I don't feel like a member of the corporate family.
3-5	The enterprise I work in means a lot to me personally.
3-6	I don't have a strong feeling that I belong to this enterprise.

(Source: Allen & Meye, 1990)

Hypotheses

This study provides hypotheses from the three dimensions of the corporate social responsibility feature, namely, organizational commitment, organizational identification and organization-based self-esteem.

(i) The relationship between corporate social responsibility feature and organizational identification.

H1a. The stronger the corporate social responsibility culture, the higher the degree of organizational identification of employees.

H1b. The stronger the corporate social responsibility atmosphere, the higher the degree of organizational identification of employees.

H1c. The better the corporate social responsibility performance, the higher the level of organizational identification of employees.

(ii) The relationship between the corporate social responsibility feature and the organization based self esteem.

H2a. The stronger the corporate social responsibility culture, the higher the organization based self-esteem of employees.

H2b. The stronger the corporate social responsibility atmosphere, the higher the organization based self-esteem of employees.

H2c. The better the corporate social responsibility performance, the higher the organization based self-esteem of employees.

(iii) The relationship between organizational identification and organizational commitment.

H3. The higher the employee's organizational identification level, the stronger the employee's organizational commitment will be.

(iv) By reviewing the relationship between corporate social responsibility feature, organizational identification, organizational commitment and other variables, this study provides the following hypotheses:

H4a. Corporate social responsibility culture indirectly and positively affects employees' organizational commitment willingness through organizational identification.

H4b. Corporate social responsibility atmosphere indirectly and positively affects employees' organizational commitment willingness through organizational identification.

H4c. Corporate social responsibility performance indirectly and positively affects employees' organizational commitment willingness through organizational identification.

(v) The relationship between organization based self esteem and organizational commitment.

H5. The higher the employee's organization based self-esteem, the stronger the employee's organizational commitment will be.

(vi) By reviewing the relationship between corporate social responsibility feature, organizational identification, organizational commitment and other variables, this study provides the following hypotheses:

H6a. Corporate social responsibility culture indirectly and positively affects employees' organizational commitment willingness through organization based self-esteem.

H6b. Corporate social responsibility atmosphere indirectly and positively affects employees' organizational commitment willingness through organization based self-esteem.

H6c. Corporate social responsibility performance indirectly and positively affects employees' organizational commitment willingness through organization based self-esteem.

(vii) The relationship between the corporate social responsibility feature and the organizational commitment.

H7a. The stronger the corporate social responsibility culture, the higher the degree of organizational commitment of employees.

H7b. The stronger the corporate social responsibility atmosphere, the higher the degree of organizational commitment of employees.

H7c. The stronger the corporate social responsibility performance, the higher the degree of organizational commitment of employees.

(viii) The relationship between organizational identification and organization based self esteem.

H8. The higher the employee's level of organizational identification, the higher the employee's level of organization based self-esteem.

Research Framework

Based on the social exchange theory, organizational justice theory, corporate reporting theory, ethical motivation theory, and enterprise soft power theory this study combs the relationship between core variables and puts forward research hypotheses. Then, along with the two aspects of the corporate social responsibility features' impact on employees' psychological perception (OBSE & OI), and then from the research idea of employees' psychological perception to employees' organizational commitment, explore the internal mechanism of the CSR's impact on employees' organizational commitment. Figure 1 is the conceptual framework of this study.

Figure 1 Research framework

Methodology
Research Design

This study chooses positivism as the research philosophy. The positivism paradigm is a rigorous and mature theoretical system and practical norms based on empiricism, objectivism and naturalism. Its spiritual essence is scientism, and its action program promotes the "scientization" of the discipline. At the same time, this study belongs to the causal study in the design of a conclusive study. A causality study is a study conducted to determine the scope and nature of causality. Causality studies can assess a particular change's impact on existing norms, processes, etc. Causality research focuses on analyzing a particular situation or a specific problem to explain the relationship between variables. In this study, the construction enterprises in Guangdong Province are taken as the sample target, and the corporate social responsibility characteristics are taken as the independent variables to study the three dimensions of corporate social responsibility characteristics. Furthermore, using organizational commitment as the dependent variable, this study proposes two mediators, namely organizational identification and organization-based self-esteem, through the relationship between dependent and independent variables to explore the causal relationship between these groups of variables. Based on the social exchange theory, organizational justice theory, corporate reporting theory, ethical motivation theory and enterprise soft power theory, this study sets research questions through problems in SOP to obtain research objectives. Furthermore, this study reviews the literature according to the research objectives and puts forward research hypotheses. The purpose of this chapter is to gradually clarify the data collection and analysis methods that need to be clear to verify the research hypopaper to complete this study. Figure 2 is the research design of this study.

Figure 2 Research Design

Population/Sampling/Unit of Analysis

According to the data released by the Guangdong Provincial Bureau of Statistics (2022), as of the first quarter of 2022, the number of construction enterprises in Guangdong Province was 9,805, and the average number of people engaged in construction activities was about 2,083,300. The theme of this study is the impact of corporate social responsibility features of construction enterprises in Guangdong Province on employees' organizational commitment. Therefore, the unit of analysis is an individual, specifically referring to legal labor workers engaged in construction activities in the construction industry in Guangdong Province. Therefore, the population in this study is 2,083,300. According to the sampling standard stipulated by Krejcie and Morgan (1970), the number of samples to be sampled per 1 million people is 384. Combined with the number of employees in construction enterprises in Guangdong Province, the sample size of this study should be 800. Therefore, this study takes 20 construction enterprises in Guangdong Province as the sampling frame, and adopts the method of random sampling for sample selection. This study collects primary data through questionnaires. Among the re distributed questionnaires, a total of 800 were distributed, 650 were collected, and 610 were effective. The effective questionnaire recovery rate was 76.25%.

Profile of Respondents

In order to ensure the rigor of the study, the samples of this study are classified according to the enterprise level (enterprise nature and enterprise scale) and the individual level (gender, age, position, education, monthly income, working time).As shown in Table 7:

Table 7 Statistics of demographic characteristics of respondents

Characteristics	Statistics	Frequency	Percentage
Nature of Enterprise	Private enterprise	10	50%
	State-owned enterprise	8	40%
	Foreign enterprise	2	10%
	Total	20	100%
Enterprise Scale	Small scale	3	15%
	Medium scale	12	60%
	Large scale	5	25%
	Total	20	100%
Gender	Male	312	51.1%
	Female	298	48.8%
	Total	610	100%
Age	Under 20 years old	13	2.1%
	20-30 years old	343	56.2%
	31-40 years old	187	30.7%
	41-50 years old	56	9.2%
	Over 50 years old	11	1.8%
	Total	610	100%
Position	Workers	289	47.4%
	First-line Managers	141	23.1%
	Middle Managers	137	22.5%
	Senior Managers	43	4.7%
	Total	610	100%
Educational Background	Junior middle school and below	24	3.9%
	High school and technical secondary school	55	9.0%
	Junior college	170	27.9%
	Undergraduate	261	42.8%
	Graduate	100	16.4%
	Total	610	100.0%
Monthly Income	Below 3000	114	18.7%
	3000-4999	164	26.9%
	5000-6999	117	19.2%
	7000 - 8999	108	17.7%
	9000 and above	107	17.5%

	Total	610	100.0%
Length of Service	Less than 1 year	106	17.4%
	1-3 years	127	20.8%
	3-5 years	149	24.4%
	5-7 years	58	9.5%
	More than 7 years	170	27.9%
	Total	610	100.0%

(Source: Author)

The Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility Features on Organizational Identification and Organization Based Self-esteem

In this study, organizational identification and organization based self-esteem are mediators of the impact of corporate social responsibility features on organizational commitment. For mediator's test, correlation and partial correlation analysis can be used. The specific process can be divided into the following four steps. (1) Test the correlation between independent variables and mediator; (2) Test the correlation between independent variables and dependent variables; (3) Examine the correlation between mediator and dependent variables; (4) Consider the degree of influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable when mediator acts: is it weakened or not? If the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable weakens to an insignificant level, it means that the mediator plays a full mediating role, and the independent variable completely influences the dependent variable through the mediator; If it weakens but still reaches the significance level, it means that mediator only plays a part of mediating role, that is, only part of the influence of independent variables on dependent variables is realized through mediator (Qu et al., 2017). At this time, the independent variable not only affects the dependent variable through mediator, but also directly affects the dependent variable. Pearson correlation analysis method is used for the test of the correlation between independent variables and mediator. The software tool used for the test is SPSS15.0. The results are shown in Table 8.

Table 8 Correlation Analysis Results of Independent Variables and Mediator

Independent Variable	Organizational Identification	Organization Based Self-esteem
Corporate social responsibility culture	.741**	.600**
Corporate social responsibility atmosphere	.676**	.619**
Corporate social responsibility performance	.620**	.568**

Note: ** means $P < 0.01$

(Source: Author)

Corporate social responsibility features include corporate social responsibility culture, corporate social responsibility atmosphere and corporate social responsibility performance (Lv, 2011). In this study, the three dimensions were taken as independent variables and organizational identification as dependent variables, and the relationship between them was tested by multiple regression analysis. After three regressions, all three independent variables entered the regression equation. It can be seen from Table 9 that the modified $R^2 = 0.631$, that is, the four variables entering the regression equation explain 63.1% of the total variation of the dependent variable. It can be further seen from Table 10 that the significance probability of F statistics is $p = 0.000 < 0.01$, that is, the original assumption that the overall regression coefficients are all 0 is rejected. Therefore, the final regression equation should include these three variables, and the overall regression effect is ideal. It can be seen from the table that the significance probability of the t-statistics of the corporate social responsibility culture dimension and the corporate social responsibility atmosphere dimension is less than 0.01, and the significance probability of the t-statistics of the corporate social responsibility performance dimension is equal to 0.01 but less than 0.05, and the t-statistics are all greater than 2.

Therefore, these three variables have a significant impact on the dependent variable and have a good prediction effect.

Table 9 Regression Model Data of Corporate Social Responsibility Features on Organizational Identification

Model	R	R2	Adj. R2	Std. Error of the Estimate	f-statistics	p-value	Durbin-Watson
3	.797(c)	.635	.631	.57286	177.309	.000	1.700

(Source: Author)

Table 10 Regression Coefficient of Corporate Social Responsibility Features to Organizational Identification

I.V.	Un-std. Coeff.		Std. Coeff.	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	β			Tolerance	VIF
(constant)	.592	.203		2.922	.004		
CSR-Culture	.493	.044	.501	11.185	.000	.596	1.679
CSR-Atmosphere	.259	.055	.262	4.681	.000	.381	2.627
CSR-Performance	.117	.045	.140	2.610	.009	.417	2.397

(Source: Author)

After secondary regression, only two independent variables (corporate social responsibility performance and organizational identification) entered the regression equation. It can be seen from Table 11 that the modified R2 = 0.557, that is, the four variables entering the regression equation explain 55.7% of the total variation of the dependent variable. It can be further seen from Table 12 that the significance probability of F statistic is $p = 0.000 < 0.01$. Therefore, the final regression equation should include these two variables, and the overall regression effect is ideal. It can be seen from the table that the significance probability of the t-statistics of corporate social responsibility performance and organizational identification is less than 0.01, and the t-statistics are greater than 2. Therefore, both variables have a significant impact on the dependent variable and have a good prediction effect.

Table 11 Regression Model Data of Corporate Social Responsibility Features on Organization Based Self-esteem

Model	R	R2	Adj. R2	Std. Error of the Estimate	f-statistics	p-value	Durbin-Watson
3	.748(b)	.560	.557	.64178	195.125	0.000	1.709

(Source: Author)

Table 12 Regression Coefficient of Corporate Social Responsibility Features to Organization Based Self-esteem

I.V.	Un-std. Coeff.		Std. Coeff.	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	β			Tolerance	VIF
(constant)	.744	.219		3.404	.001		
CSR-Culture	.582	.053	.412	2.421	.123	.421	.531
CSR-Atmosphere	.231	.421	.351	3.123	.285	.421	1.432
CSR-Performance	.237	.052	.234	4.560	.000	.543	1.841

(Source: Author)

According to the regression equation, corporate social responsibility culture has a significant effect on organizational identification ($P = 0.501$), and H1a is supported; Corporate social responsibility atmosphere has a significant effect on organizational identification ($P = 0.262$), and H1b is supported; Corporate social responsibility performance has a significant effect on organizational identification ($P = 0.140$), and H1c is supported. It can be concluded from Table 12 that the significance of corporate social responsibility culture and corporate social responsibility atmosphere is greater than 0.1, so these two dimensions are not significant

influencing factors. That is, corporate social responsibility culture has no significant effect on organization based self-esteem, and H2a is not supported; Corporate social responsibility atmosphere has no significant effect on organization based self-esteem, and H2b is not supported; Corporate social responsibility performance has a significant effect on organization based self-esteem (0 = 0.234), and H2c is supported. Organizational identification has a significant effect on organization based self-esteem (P = 0.570), and H8 is supported.

The Influence of Organizational Identification and Organization Based Self-esteem on Organizational Commitment

Pearson correlation analysis method is used to test the correlation between the two mediators and dependent variable in this study. The software tool used for the test is SPSS15.0. The results are shown in Table13:

Table 13 Correlation Analysis Results of Mediators and Dependent Variable

	Organizational Commitment
Organizational Identification	.697**
Organization Based Self-esteem	.611**

Note: ** means P<0.01
(Source: Author)

From the analysis results in the above table, both organizational identification and organization-based self-esteem have significant correlation with organizational commitment.

Table 14 Regression Model Data of Organizational Identification and Organization Based Self-esteem on Organizational Commitment

Model	R	R2	Adj. R2	Std. Error of the Estimate	f-statistics	p-value	Durbin-Watson
3	.748(b)	.560	.557	.64178	195.125	0.000	1.709

(Source: Author)

Table 15 Regression Coefficient of Organizational Identification and Organization Based Self-esteem on Organizational Commitment

I.V.	Un-std. Coeff.		Std. Coeff.	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	β			Tolerance	VIF
(constant)	-.535	.275		-1.945	.053		
Organizational Identification	.284	.066	.234	4.293	.000	.509	1.965
Organization Based Self-esteem	.189	.071	.157	2.685	.008	.440	2.271

(Source: Author)

The following table shows the regression analysis between organizational identification and organization based self-esteem.

Table 16 Regression Coefficient of Organizational Identification on Organization Based Self-esteem

I.V.	Un-std. Coeff.		Std. Coeff.	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	β			Tolerance	VIF
Organizational Identification	.231	.061	.570	4.124	.000	.302	1.495

(Source: Author)

Organizational identification has a significant effect on organizational commitment (P=0.234), and H3 is supported; Organization based self-esteem has a significant effect on organizational commitment (P=0.157), and H5 is supported; Organizational identification has a significant effect on organization based self-esteem (P=0.570), and H8 is supported.

The Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility Features on Organizational Commitment

Pearson correlation analysis method is used to test the correlation of corporate social response features on organizational commitment. The software tool used for the test is SPSS15.0. The results are shown in Table 17:

Table 17 Correlation Analysis Results of Independent Variable and Dependent Variable

Variables	Organizational Commitment
Corporate social responsibility culture	.573**
Corporate social responsibility atmosphere	.618**
Corporate social responsibility performance	.496**

Note: ** means $P < 0.01$

(Source: Author)

From the analysis results in the above table, there is a significant correlation between the three independent variable dimensions of culture, atmosphere and performance with the organizational commitment.

Table 18 Regression Coefficient of Corporate Social Responsibility Features to Organizational Commitment

I.V.	Un-std. Coeff.		Std. Coeff.	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	β			Tolerance	VIF
CSR-Culture	.321	.472	.212	2.412	.142	.341	2.451
CSR-Atmosphere	.472	.537	.301	4.211	.204	.241	3.214
CSR-Performance	.521	.077	.424	6.785	.000	.388	2.577

(Source: Author)

According to the data in Table 18, the significance of corporate social responsibility culture and corporate social responsibility atmosphere is greater than 0.1, so they have no significant impact on organizational commitment. That is, there is no significant correlation between corporate social responsibility culture and corporate social responsibility atmosphere with organizational commitment. Therefore, both H7a and H7b are not supported; It can be seen from the regression equation that corporate social responsibility performance has a significant effect on organizational commitment ($P=0.424$), and H7c is supported.

The Mediating Role of Organizational Identification and Organization Based Self-esteem

In this section, organizational identification and organization based self esteem are used as control variables, and partial correlation analysis is conducted on the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables to investigate the change of correlation between independent variables and dependent variables. The results of partial correlation analysis are shown in Table 19:

Table 19 Partial Correlation Analysis Results of Independent Variables and Dependent Variable

Variables	Organizational Commitment
Corporate social responsibility culture	.093
Corporate social responsibility atmosphere	.072
Corporate social responsibility performance	.238**

Note: ** means $P < 0.01$

(Source: Author)

Table 20 Regression Model Data of Corporate Social Responsibility Features on Organizational Commitment

Model	R	R2	Adj. R2	Std. Error of the Estimate	f-statistics	p-value	Durbin-Watson
3	.732	.536	.532	.79341	118.057	0.000	1.642

(Source: Author)

Table 21 Regression Coefficient of Corporate Social Responsibility Features to Organizational Commitment

Variables	Un-std. Coeff.		Std. Coeff.	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	β			Tolerance	VIF
(constant)	-.535	.275		-1.945	.053		
CSR-Culture	.521	.077	.424	6.785	.000	.388	2.577
Organizational Identification	.284	.066	.234	4.293	.000	.509	1.965
Organization Based Self-esteem	.189	.071	.157	2.685	.008	.440	2.271

(Source: Author)

Based on the above analysis and results, it can be seen that corporate social responsibility culture has no significant effect on organization-based self-esteem, so H6a is not supported, and corporate social responsibility atmosphere has no significant impact on organization based self-esteem, so H6b is not supported, but H4a, H4b, H4c, and H6c are supported.

Conclusion

(1) The direct impact of corporate social responsibility features on employees' organizational commitment. Empirical analysis shows that corporate social responsibility performance in corporate social responsibility features has a direct impact on organizational commitment ($\beta = 0.424$, $P < 0.001$), corporate social responsibility atmosphere has no direct impact on organizational commitment. This shows that corporate social responsibility performance can make employees feel a sense of organizational justice, which is conducive to employees making long-term ethical decisions about the organization, thus affecting employees' organizational commitment level. In addition, it also shows that the impact of corporate social responsibility features on the organizational commitment of employees occurs more through the mediating role of organizational identification and organization based self esteem, which is a relatively complex psychological mechanism process than a simple direct impact (Li & Zuo 2021).

(2) The impact of corporate social responsibility features on organizational identification. Corporate social responsibility culture has a significant positive impact on organizational identification ($\beta = 0.501$, $p < 0.001$); Corporate social responsibility atmosphere has a significant positive impact on organizational identification ($\beta = 0.262$, $P < 0.001$), and corporate social responsibility performance had a significant positive impact on organizational identification ($\beta = 0.140$, $p < 0.01$). This shows that all aspects of corporate social responsibility features can affect employees' psychological perception through ethical incentives, organizational justice, organizational support and care perception, and reputation perception, which significantly affect employees' organizational identification. It can be seen that the path coefficient of corporate social responsibility culture on organizational identification is the largest ($\beta = 0.501$, $P < 0.001$), followed by corporate social responsibility atmosphere ($\beta = 0.262$, $P < 0.001$), while corporate social responsibility performance had the smallest ($\beta = 0.140$, $p < 0.01$). This shows that employees' sense of organizational identification comes more from their recognition of the core values, missions and goals of the organization's social responsibility. Only when the core values of the enterprise's social responsibility match the values of employees, can employees deeply recognize the values of the enterprise's social responsibility,

the ambitious goal of serving the society, and the strategy of harmonious common development. Employees' sense of organizational identification comes from their perception of corporate social responsibility atmosphere. This shows that under the background that China attaches importance to the relationship between superiors and subordinates and the relationship between colleagues, enterprises can help employees understand corporate social responsibility culture, corporate mission and strategic objectives by creating a responsible atmosphere of organizational care and support and good communication, achieve psychological integration with the organization, and enhance the sense of organizational identification. Of course, corporate social responsibility performance itself can also affect organizational identification, but the impact is relatively weak compared with social responsibility culture and atmosphere.

(3) The impact of corporate social responsibility features on organization based self-esteem. Corporate social responsibility culture has no significant effect on organization based self-esteem. At the same time, corporate social responsibility atmosphere has no significant effect on organization based self-esteem. Only corporate social responsibility performance has a significant positive impact on organization based self-esteem ($\beta = 0.234$, $p < 0.001$). This shows that although organization based self-esteem is a relatively stable variable, which is not easily affected by the responsibility culture and the responsibility atmosphere, the actual responsibility actions of the enterprise to the stakeholders can make employees impact their stable psychological state through the perception of organizational justice and reputation. At the same time, organizational identification also has a significant positive impact on organization based self-esteem ($\beta = 0.570$, $p < 0.001$). This shows that employees' high recognition of the organization will lead to their initiative consciousness of being the main member of the organization, and then hope to gain the appreciation and sense of value of others through their own efforts and achievements, thus generating a high level of organization based self-esteem. In addition, from the data test results, it is not that corporate social responsibility culture and atmosphere have no impact on organization based self-esteem, but that organization based self-esteem is a relatively stable psychological variable. Organization based self-esteem needs to have a deep impact on organization based self-esteem through the practical actions of corporate social responsibility, the high reputation it brings, the perception of organizational justice, and the deep recognition of corporate social responsibility culture and atmosphere. It can be seen that organization based self-esteem is a relatively stable and slow psychological variable, and enterprises need to comprehensively increase corporate social responsibility to improve the level of organization based self-esteem of employees. However, it is precisely because of this that once the organization based self-esteem level of employees is improved, they will also maintain relative stability at a high level, which will profoundly affect the behavior and attitude of employees, make Pro organization behavior and loyalty to the organization. And from the data, we can also see the path coefficient of organizational identification to organization based self-esteem ($\beta = 0.570$, $P < 0.001$) is much larger than the path coefficient of corporate social responsibility performance ($\beta = 0.234$, $P < 0.001$). This shows that although corporate social responsibility culture and atmosphere have no direct impact on organization based self-esteem, they ultimately indirectly affect organization based self-esteem through organizational identification, and the impact is still relatively strong. This also shows that in order to improve the level of organization-based self-esteem of employees, enterprises should not only pay attention to the direct impact of the practice of corporate social responsibility performance on organization based self-esteem, but also pay attention to the indirect impact of corporate social responsibility culture and the shaping of atmosphere on organization based self-esteem.

(4) Organizational identification and organization based self-esteem are mediating effects between corporate social responsibility features and organizational commitment. Since organizational identification has a completely mediating role between the dimension of corporate social responsibility culture and organizational commitment, and corporate social responsibility culture has no significant relationship with organization based self-esteem, it is clear that corporate social responsibility culture positively affects employee commitment through organizational identification. The mechanism of action is that corporate social responsibility culture can generate effective ethical incentives, so that employees' values and goals can be deeply recognized and aligned with the values and goals of the organization, and then the internal essence of corporate social responsibility can be internalized into their own hearts, so as to improve employees' organizational commitment level. Since organizational identification has a completely mediating effect between the corporate social responsibility atmosphere dimension and the organizational commitment, the corporate social responsibility atmosphere dimension does not significantly affect the organization based self-esteem. It indicates that corporate social responsibility atmosphere positively affects employee commitment through organizational identification. The mechanism of action is that corporate social responsibility atmosphere creates a harmonious and unobstructed communication atmosphere through the care and support of the organization for employees, so that employees can imperceptibly feel the internal spiritual quality of corporate social responsibility, thereby generating a high level of organizational identification for enterprises, and then a high level of organizational commitment. Organizational identification and organization based self-esteem have some mediating roles in the relationship between corporate social responsibility performance and organizational commitment. This shows that corporate social responsibility performance can directly affect the organizational commitment level of employees, or indirectly affect the organizational commitment level of employees through organizational identification and the mediating role of organization based self-esteem. The mechanism is that corporate social responsibility performance affects employees' organizational commitment level by affecting their psychological perception. It shows that employees will go through a complex psychological process before forming an organizational commitment. Through the observation of corporate social responsibility performance, they have a profound value recognition of the intrinsic nature of corporate social responsibility shown therein. According to the normalized regression equation (as shown below):

$$\text{Organizational Commitment} = 0.424 * \text{Corporate Social Responsibility Performance} + 0.234 * \text{Organizational Identification} + 0.157 * \text{Organization Based Self-esteem}$$

From the above equation, it can be concluded that corporate social responsibility performance has the largest impact on organizational commitment, followed by organizational identification, and the smallest is organization based self-esteem. This also shows that only when an enterprise truly implements its social responsibility and allows employees to truly feel the internal quality of corporate social responsibility, employees will entrust their feelings to the enterprise from the bottom of their hearts and be loyal to the enterprise.

(5) The age and income level of employees are the control variables affecting organization based self-esteem and organizational identification. The results of empirical analysis show that the age of employees has a significant difference on employees' self-esteem, but has no significant difference on organizational identification and organizational commitment. It can be seen from the analysis results that the "41-50 year old" age group has the strongest organization based self-esteem, the "over 50 year old" age group has the second place, and the other age groups are general. Therefore, enterprises should take measures to cultivate the sense of organization based self-esteem of young employees, maintain the sense of organization based self-esteem of old employees who are about to retire, and entrust middle-

aged employees with important tasks to give full play to their high-level sense of organization based self-esteem (Jiang & Wong 2022). The results of empirical analysis show that the monthly income of employees has a significant difference and impact on employees' organizational identification, but has no significant difference and impact on organization based self-esteem and organizational commitment. It can be seen from the analysis results that for organizational identification, there is no significant difference between the salary levels of "9000 and above" and the middle and high salary levels of "5000-6999" and "7000-8999", but there is a significant difference between "3000 and below" and "3000-4999". This shows that if an employee's income is difficult to maintain the most basic life, it is difficult to ask the employee organization to make selfless contributions (Su & Zang 2021). Employees will further pursue higher-level needs only after meeting the most basic survival needs. Therefore, the enterprises that really do a good job in corporate social responsibility can only be those that have excellent financial conditions, put people first and put the needs of employees at heart. Good social responsibility will further promote the realization of good financial performance through the organizational loyalty of employees, thus forming a virtuous cycle of mutual promotion between financial performance and social responsibility (Ge 2020; Gu 2022).

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